

Long-lasting effects of in utero heat stress on subsequent performances of heifers and primiparous cows

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ABSTRACT

The performance of an adult dairy cow may be influenced by heat stress that occurs during her gestation. The present study investigated potential effects of temperature-humidity index (THI) experienced by a cow during pregnancy on the gestated daughter's performance on her first lactation, for the French Holstein and Montbéliarde dairy cattle populations. We analyzed 14 traits, all measured on genotyped cows: 305-d milk, fat, and protein yields; 305-d SCS; clinical mastitis (both occurrence and number of events); body conformation traits; and heifer and cow conception rate. To study the effect of heat stress, we considered the THI experienced by the gestating cow, averaged for each month of her pregnancy and then categorized in 7 classes (≤ 40 , [40,45], [45,50], [50,55], [55,60], [60,65], and >65). These average THI classes were then fitted as categorical covariates in the regression models used for this study, which included other fixed effects, and the GEBV as a covariate, both specific to each trait, the latter being previously obtained from the official French evaluations. The THI effect was therefore estimated as the deviation between the observed and predicted performances. In general, the estimated heat stress effects were small, presenting limited practical impact on the studied traits, and particularly for fertility and udder health, the estimated heat stress effects were not statistically significant. For the production traits (i.e., milk, fat, and protein yields), the estimated effect associated with high THI experienced at the beginning of the gestation was negative, and slightly positive when associated with high THI experienced by the dam at the end of her pregnancy. Finally, our results suggest that under the current French climate conditions, heat stress experienced by cows during any stage of their

pregnancy has limited impact on the future performance of their gestated daughters; however, we cannot exclude that a significant in utero heat stress effect may be present in climate conditions warmer than the French.

Key words: dairy cattle, prenatal effects, environmental effects, temperature-humidity index, fetal programming

INTRODUCTION

Climate change is expected to have major negative consequences for livestock production. One of the main risks will come from heatwaves, which will become more frequent and intense. Exposure to very hot environments can challenge cattle homeothermy, thereby inducing heat stress (Shephard and Maloney, 2023) and the onset of behavioral, physical, biochemical, and physiological processes as a response to counteract the negative effects of heat stress and maintain thermal equilibrium (Silanikove, 2000; Collier et al., 2017). Among these processes responding to heat stress, some, such as panting, sweating, or greater chemical reaction rates, can increase maintenance requirements in cattle (Baumgard and Rhoads, 2012). On the other hand, a decrease in feed intake due to heat exposure is an adaptive mechanism to decrease diet-induced thermogenesis (Kadzere et al., 2002; Collier et al., 2017). In addition to these direct responses to heat stress, and as a consequence of many of them, animals exposed to heat stress present a decrease in productivity, with negative short-term effects of heat stress reported for many commercial cattle traits, such as production, reproduction, and health or welfare traits (Polsky and Von Keyserlingk, 2017; Lees et al., 2019; Vinet et al., 2023, 2024).

For pregnant cows, an increase of their core body temperature may affect not only the cow's own performance, but also the gestated offspring (De Rensis and Scaramuzzi, 2003; Wolfenson and Roth, 2019). Heat stress compromises the intrauterine environment, with a decrease in blood flow to the uterus and an increase

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in uterine temperature (De Rensis and Scaramuzzi, 2003). Several authors reported that heat stress inhibits embryonic development, increases early embryonic loss, and reduces the proportion of successful inseminations (Roth, 2008; De Rensis et al., 2015; Hansen, 2019). High ambient temperature also affects the pre-attachment stage of embryos. Nevertheless, as pregnancy progresses, embryos become more resistant to the adverse effects of maternal heat stress (Wolfenson and Roth, 2019). It is generally believed that fetal temperature is completely dependent on the maternal temperature (Asakura, 2004) because the body temperature of the fetus is dependent on its metabolic heat production and on the heat transfer with the dam. The fetus exchanges heat with the dam mainly through the fetal-placental circulation, a process that accounts for approximately 85% of total fetal heat loss; the remaining heat is exchanged conductively through fetal membranes, amniotic fluid, and the uterine wall (Asakura, 2004). Consequently, changes in maternal core temperature affect fetal temperature.

When pregnancy is carried to term, heat stress may have long-term effects on the calf's performance, including postnatal survival and its adult performance up to the third lactation (Pinedo and De Vries, 2017; Ouellet et al., 2021). With a previous study, we showed that in mainland France, a temperate climate zone, dairy cows experience a decline in their overall performance immediately after a temperature-humidity index (THI) increase (Vinet et al., 2023). We therefore wondered whether in utero heat stress could happen for the French dairy cattle breeds, even in our temperate climate.

The present study aimed to assess if heat stress during the dam's pregnancy has a time-lagged effect on the subsequent daughter's performances (for both heifers and primiparous cows), to determine the potential magnitude of the effect and to identify the most critical period and level of heat stress for the embryo/fetus.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Ethics Statement

This study was carried out with existing data collected on commercial farm and no experiment was performed on animals. Thus, no ethical approval was required.

Animal Data

The animal data used in this study, comprising the insemination and calving dates of the dams, the performances of their offspring, and the pedigree information, were extracted from the French national database (INRAE-CTIG, Jouy-en-Josas). The start and end dates of gestation were deducted from the date of successful

insemination of the dam and the date of birth of the offspring. Gestations shorter than 270 d or longer than 294 d for Holstein or 300 d for Montbéliarde were excluded from the analysis. The offspring performance data used were from animals born between 2015 and 2020. The dams and their offspring were purebred cows from either the French Holstein (HOL) or Montbéliarde (MON) populations, and each breed was studied separately.

The progeny traits analyzed for both breeds were conception rate after the first insemination for heifers (CRh) and cows (CRc); 305-d milk (MY), fat (FY), and protein yields (PY); 305-d SCS; clinical mastitis occurrence (Mast) and number of clinical mastitis events (MastNb); height at sacrum; body depth; and chest width. For the French HOL breed, BCS was also analyzed, and for the MON breed, muscularity at thighs (MuscT) and at withers (MuscW) was also analyzed. Except for CRh, all traits were measured during the first lactation. For each studied trait, the contemporary groups (either herd-year or herd-date-of-visit, depending on the trait) with fewer than 3 cows were removed. Depending on the trait, the final data set contained between 97,815 and 419,624 HOL offspring and between 23,826 and 149,987 MON offspring. Descriptive statistics of the studied traits are presented in Table 1.

Values for CRh and CRc were determined as in Barbat et al. (2010): the outcome was set to 100 (i.e., successful) if the cow calved following the expected gestation length of the breed (281 ± 15 d and 285 ± 15 d for Holstein and Montbéliarde respectively), otherwise it was set to 0. Only purebred inseminations were considered. For heifers, only first inseminations performed between 12 and 28 mo of age were kept. For primiparous cows, only those that calved between 22 and 40 mo of age and that were first inseminated between 15 and 200 d after calving were retained.

All 305-d production traits and SCS records were discarded for lactations lasting less than 250 d. The 305-d SCS was obtained by averaging test-day SCS records, with test-day SCS being a log-transformation of the test-day records of SCC: $SCS = \log_2(SCC/100,000) + 3$ (Ali and Shook, 1980).

Clinical mastitis occurrence was a binary trait with value 1 when at least one clinical mastitis event was detected during the first 150 d of the lactation, and 0 otherwise; MastNb is the number of occurrences of clinical mastitis during the first 150 DIM. To ensure that the health information was sufficiently complete, only herd-year combinations with a mastitis incidence of at least 10% in primiparous cows were included.

The morphological traits were recorded by classifiers accredited by the breeding organizations. For Holstein, morphological traits were scored from 1 to 9. For Montbéliarde, the muscularity traits were scored, whereas the

Table 1. Number of females (with means and SD) by trait in Holstein and Montbéliarde

Item	Holstein			Montbéliarde		
	Number	Mean	SD	Number	Mean	SD
Milk yield (kg)	214,151	7,876	1,467	69,848	6,825	1,268
Fat yield (kg)	214,151	315	58	69,848	265	52
Protein yield (kg)	214,151	254	48	69,848	228	44
SCS	213,405	2.033	1.215	69,796	2.203	1.278
Mastitis occurrence	97,815	0.14	0.34	23,826	0.12	0.33
Mastitis number	97,815	0.18	0.52	23,826	0.15	0.46
Conception rate for heifers (%)	419,624	57.3	49.5	149,987	58.3	49.3
Conception rate for cows (%)	284,337	49.0	50.0	76,678	56.1	49.6
Height at sacrum ¹	105,883	6.33	1.53	49,795	145.89	3.82
Body depth ¹	105,883	5.74	1.20	49,795	74.74	2.56
Chest width ¹	105,883	5.25	1.05	49,795	44.17	3.34
BCS ²	105,883	4.62	1.08			
Muscularity at thighs ³				49,795	5.38	1.74
Muscularity at withers ³				49,795	5.33	2.05

¹The unit of measurement of these traits depends on the breed: a score from 1 to 9 (the greater the height, depth, or width, the higher the score) for Holstein, and a distance in cm for Montbéliarde.

²Measured with a score from 1 (thinnest) to 9 (fattest).

³Measured with a score from 1 (narrow withers/hollow thighs) to 9 (broad withers/rounded thighs).

other traits (i.e., height at sacrum, body depth and chest width) were measured.

Meteorological Data

The meteorological data used for this study were the Système d'Analyse Fournissant des Renseignements Atmosphériques à la Neige (SAFRAN) data, provided by the French national meteorological agency (Météo-France). These data contain daily interpolated estimates of various climate variables for each one (9,892 total) of the 8 × 8-km squares that cover the entire French territory. These daily interpolated estimates of climate variables are the result of a model developed for meteorological forecasting based on continuous local recording from a wide network of meteorological stations. As in Vinet et al. (2023), the daily meteorological data assigned to each herd (geographically identified by its postal code) were weighted averages of the values at each of the 8 × 8-km squares that covered the location, with the weights equal to the proportion of the surface of the village in each square.

The meteorological variables used in this study were the average temperature and relative humidity, combined into a single THI. The daily THI (NRC, 1971) was calculated as $THI = (1.8 \times T + 32) - (0.55 - 0.0055 \times RH) \times (1.8 \times T - 26)$, where T is the 24-h mean temperature (°C), and RH is the 24-h mean relative humidity (%). The climate heat stress variable, whose effects were to be assessed, was the mean THI for each month of the dam's pregnancy. In a preliminary analysis, different heat stress indicators were tested for each month or trimester of the dam's pregnancy: the mean THI, the mean maximum

temperatures (both for each month or for each trimester), and the sum of daily THI >65 or THI >70 for each month only. Because all these heat stress indicators presented similar estimated effects during the same periods of in utero development, only the results based on the average THI for each month of the dam's pregnancy are presented and discussed in this article (Supplemental Figure S1, see Notes). We kept only the data from gestations of at least 270 d with all THI information available for gestational mo 1 to 9 (**M1–M9**, with M1 spanning from d 1 to 30, M2 spanning from d 31 to 60, and so on up to M9 spanning from d 241 to 270). To assess a possible effect of heat stress during the very last period of the gestation, an additional period (**M9.5**) was considered. This period spanned from d 250 to 279. For each month of gestation, mean THI values ranged from 26 or 27 to 73 or 74, with at least 6.3% of the mean THI values above 65 (Table 2).

Statistical Analyses

This study was based on a comparison between observed and predicted performances. The performances were predicted by regression on the GEBV in addition to the usual fixed effects. Specifically, the following model was used:

$$\mathbf{y} = \mathbf{X}\boldsymbol{\beta} + \mathbf{W}\mathbf{h} + \mathbf{a}\mathbf{g} + \mathbf{e}, \quad [1]$$

where \mathbf{y} is the vector of the observed performances of the female offspring for a given trait; $\boldsymbol{\beta}$ is the vector of the fixed effects similar to those used in the French routine genetic evaluation (International Bull Evaluation Service, <https://interbull.org/ib/geforms>; Supplemental

Table 2. Number of observations in the THI >65 class and percentage of observations (shown in parentheses) in this THI >65 class out of the total number of performances, for each month of gestation and each trait, for the Holstein (HOL) and the Montbéliarde (MON) breeds

Item, n (%)	Month of gestation of the dam												
	M1	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6	M7	M8	M9	M9.5			
Milk, protein, and fat yields, and SCS													
HOL	15,118 (7.1)	16,671 (7.8)	18,532 (8.7)	20,494 (9.6)	23,566 (11)	26,867 (12.5)	29,277 (13.7)	28,938 (13.5)	24,488 (11.4)	23,339 (10.9)			
MON	4,828 (6.9)	5,098 (7.3)	5,659 (8.1)	6,897 (9.9)	8,893 (12.7)	10,796 (15.5)	12,488 (17.9)	13,363 (19.1)	11,106 (15.9)	9,995 (14.3)			
Type traits													
HOL	7,256 (6.9)	8,013 (7.6)	9,100 (8.6)	10,249 (9.7)	11,637 (11)	13,129 (12.4)	14,535 (13.7)	14,778 (14)	12,783 (12.1)	12,098 (11.4)			
MON	3,160 (6.3)	3,379 (6.8)	3,719 (7.5)	4,479 (9)	5,638 (11.3)	6,764 (13.6)	7,671 (15.4)	8,310 (16.7)	6,938 (13.9)	6,236 (12.5)			
Mastitis traits													
HOL	6,393 (6.5%)	7,019 (7.2%)	7,819 (8%)	8,745 (8.9%)	10,077 (10.3%)	11,509 (11.8%)	12,787 (13.1%)	12,549 (12.8%)	10,625 (10.9%)	10,076 (10.3%)			
MON	1,843 (7.7%)	1,970 (8.2%)	2,246 (9.4%)	2,759 (11.5%)	3,526 (14.7%)	4,255 (17.8%)	4,920 (20.6%)	5,118 (21.4%)	4,161 (17.4%)	3,739 (15.6%)			
Conception rate for heifers													
HOL	27,733 (6.6)	29,647 (7.1)	31,870 (7.6)	34,758 (8.3)	43,418 (10.3)	52,464 (12.5)	56,525 (13.5)	56,399 (13.4)	49,359 (11.8)	46,852 (11.2)			
MON	10,331 (6.9)	10,983 (7.3)	11,979 (8)	14,315 (9.5)	18,246 (12.2)	22,051 (14.7)	24,913 (16.6)	26,781 (17.9)	22,801 (15.2)	20,652 (13.8)			
Conception rate for cows													
HOL	20,365 (7.2)	22,269 (7.8)	24,360 (8.6)	26,883 (9.5)	30,666 (10.8)	34,883 (12.3)	37,793 (13.3)	37,618 (13.2)	32,215 (11.3)	30,773 (10.8)			
MON	5,420 (7.1)	5,757 (7.5)	6,406 (8.4)	7,696 (10)	9,770 (12.7)	11,693 (15.2)	13,342 (17.4)	14,267 (18.6)	11,798 (15.4)	10,642 (13.9)			

Table S1, see Notes), and \mathbf{X} is their incidence matrix; \mathbf{h} is the vector of monthly THI effects during the dam's gestation, in 7 classes (≤ 40 ,]40,45],]45,50],]50,55],]55,60],]60,65], and >65), and \mathbf{W} is their incidence matrix; \mathbf{g} is the vector of GEBV of the female offspring with performance in \mathbf{y} , fitted as a covariate, and \mathbf{a} is their regression coefficient; and \mathbf{e} is the vector of random residuals. The GEBV are from the French official genomic evaluations. To avoid any direct dependencies between the GEBV and the performances, the March 2018 evaluation was used, as it did not account for the own performances of the females whose performances were used for our analyses. Finally, for each trait, separate models were fit to estimate the THI effects during each gestational month, totaling 10 individual models per trait (M1 to M9 and M9.5), with each estimating the effects of all 7 THI classes. The regression models were implemented using the GLM procedure of SAS software version 9.4 (SAS Institute Inc., 2013; Cary, NC). To account for multiple testing (420 independent tests classes of THI-month of gestation-breed-trait by group of traits: production, type, fertility, or health), the effects were deemed significant if the nominal P -value was smaller than 0.0001, corresponding to an overall P -value of 4% at the scale of the group of traits.

RESULTS

Figure 1 provides the P -values associated with the estimated effects of the mean THI by the dam's gestational month, on the progeny performances. In this figure, we observed that for both breeds, in general, the mean THI per gestational month presented a statistically significant effect on the type traits (BCS, MuscW, MuscT, height at sacrum, body depth, and Weight), MY, FY, PY, and SCS. Conversely, the mean THI per gestational month did not present a statistically significant effect on Mast, MastNb, CRc, and CRh, and results for these traits using other climate indicators did not differ in their statistical significance (Supplemental Figure S1, see Notes). Hence, further results related to these traits are mentioned only briefly in the subsequent sections.

Figures 2 to 6 present the estimated effects of mean THI during each month of gestation on the progeny's MY, FY, PY, SCS, height at sacrum, body depth, and chest width, respectively, for both breeds. Figure 7 presents the estimated effects of mean THI during each month of pregnancy on the progeny's BCS for the HOL breed only, and on MuscT and MuscW for the MON breed only. The corresponding P -values associated with the estimated effect of each monthly THI class presented in Figures 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, and 7 are available in Supplemental Table S2 (see Notes). For every trait studied, the effect of THI during

Figure 1. P -values of the effect of the average temperature-humidity index by month of the gestation of the dam on the progeny performances for both breed, Holstein (HOL, top) and Montbéliarde (MON, bottom). Results are given by colors according to nominal p -values. When accounting for the multiplicity of tests, only dark green cells indicate significant results at a 5% risk. MuscW = muscularity at withers; MuscT = muscularity at thighs; Height = height at sacrum; Depth = body depth; Width = chest width; MY = 305-d milk yield; FY = 305-d fat yield; PY = 305-d protein yield; Mast = occurrence of mastitis during the first 150 d days of lactation; MastNb = number of mastitis events; CRh = conception rate for heifers; CRc = conception rate for cows; M1–M9 = months 1 to 9 of the gestation of the dam (d 1 to d 270, in 30-d increments); M9.5 = d 250 to d 279 of the gestation of the dam.

the in utero development on the subsequent daughter's performances was low. The effect of the different THI classes during the dam's gestation on the daughter's MY was at maximum 96 kg for HOL (i.e., 1.2% of the average HOL whole lactation milk yield). This effect was obtained for the THI effect during the seventh month of the dam's gestation. It was observed between the effect of $\text{THI} \leq 40$ and the effect of $\text{THI} > 65$ on the daughters' performance. For MON, the greatest difference in MY was 72 kg, (i.e., 1.1% of the average MON whole lactation milk yield). It was observed between the second coldest and the hottest THI classes (i.e.,]40,45] and >65) during the sixth month. The direction of the THI effect varied according to the gestational stage and breed. Overall, for HOL, a high THI level had a negative effect on MY, FY, and PY only when experienced during the dam's initial months of gestation, whereas this high THI effect was positive when experienced during the dam's mid to final months of gestation (Figures 2, 3, and 4). For the MON breed, the trend was the same as observed for HOL for M1 to M8, although with weaker effects (Figures 2, 3, and 4) and some statistically nonsignificant effects (Supplemental Table S2), and we observed negative effects

Figure 2. Effect of the mean temperature-humidity index (THI) during each month of fetal development on the first lactation’s 305-d milk yield for Holstein (HOL, top) and Montbéliarde (MON, bottom). For each month of gestation, the estimated effect is the difference in kg of milk compared with the effect of the THI class [40,45]. M1–M9 = months 1 to 9 of the gestation of the dam (d 1 to d 270, in 30-d increments); M9.5 = d 250 to d 279 of the gestation of the dam.

Figure 4. Effect of the mean temperature-humidity index (THI) during each month of fetal development on the first lactation’s 305-d protein yield for Holstein (HOL, top) and Montbéliarde (MON, bottom). For each month of gestation, the estimated effect is the difference in kg of protein compared with the effect of the THI class [40,45]. M1–M9 = months 1 to 9 of the gestation of the dam (d 1 to d 270, in 30-d increments); M9.5 = d 250 to d 279 of the gestation of the dam.

Figure 3. Effect of the mean temperature-humidity index (THI) during each month of fetal development on the first lactation’s 305-d fat yield for Holstein (HOL, top) and Montbéliarde (MON, bottom). For each month of gestation, the estimated effect is the difference in kg of fat compared with the effect of the THI class [40,45]. M1–M9 = months 1 to 9 of the gestation of the dam (d 1 to d 270, in 30-d increments); M9.5 = d 250 to d 279 of the gestation of the dam.

Figure 5. Effect of the mean temperature-humidity index (THI) during each month of fetal development on the first lactation’s 305-d SCS for Holstein (HOL, top) and Montbéliarde (MON, bottom). For each month of gestation, the estimated effect is the difference in SCS compared with the effect of the THI class [40,45]. M1–M9 = months 1 to 9 of the gestation of the dam (d 1 to d 270, in 30-d increments); M9.5 = d 250 to d 279 of the gestation of the dam.

Figure 6. Effect of the mean temperature-humidity index (THI) during each month of fetal development on body conformation traits height at sacrum, body depth, and chest width for Holstein (left) and for Montbéliarde (right). For each month of gestation, the estimated effect is the difference in score (from 1 to 9, for Holstein) or measurement (in cm, for Montbéliarde) compared with the effect of the THI class]40,45]. M1–M9 = months 1 to 9 of the gestation of the dam (d 1 to d 270, in 30-d increments); M9.5 = d 250 to d 279 of the gestation of the dam.

associated with high THI levels experienced by the dam during M9 and M9.5; however, these effects were not statistically significant.

For both breeds, an unfavorable effect of a high THI was observed for SCS when experienced by the dam at

the beginning of the gestation, with a favorable effect observed when high THI was experienced by the dam at the end of the pregnancy (Figure 5). These described effects on the daughter's SCS of high THI experienced by the dam presented relatively high significance levels (Supplemental Table S2). Note that in the case of SCS, the adverse effect is an increase in SCS (reflecting an inflammatory response).

For both breeds, the morphological traits in general presented a negative effect of THI >65, when experienced by them dam during the middle of the gestation, and positive when experienced by the dam during the end of the gestation. For MON, all these traits tended to be positively influenced by a high THI during the dam's first month of pregnancy (Figure 6 and Supplemental Table S2).

To summarize, the effects of different prenatal THI on the subsequent daughter's milk performance was minor. The effects were higher for SCS and type traits. The adverse effects of high THI were mainly observed at the beginning or in the middle of the gestation of the dam. No significant effect was observed on fertility or clinical mastitis of the daughters, probably due to insufficient power.

Figure 7. Effect of the mean temperature-humidity index (THI) during each month of fetal development on BCS in Holstein (BCS - HOL) and muscularity at thighs (MuscT - MON) and at withers (MuscW - MON) for Montbéliarde. For each month of gestation, the estimated effect is the difference in BCS score (from 1 = thinnest to 9 = fattest) compared with the effect of the THI class]40,45]. M1–M9 = months 1 to 9 of the gestation of the dam (d 1 to d 270, in 30-d increments); M9.5 = d 250 to d 279 of the gestation of the dam.

DISCUSSION

This study estimated THI effects as deviations of the observed performance from the expected performance. The expected performance was fitted in the model through the linear regression of the observed performance on the GEBV from a prior evaluation that did not contain

the performances analyzed in this present study. Due to the large size of the reference populations in both the French Holstein and Montbéliarde breeds, these GEBV are considered accurate. These regression coefficients were close to their expectations, and a further detailed discussion about these regression coefficients can be found in Fouéré et al. (2024), a study of potential factors of maternal programming.

This present study highlighted very low or statistically insignificant effects of THI during the fetal stage on the later onset of clinical mastitis and on fertility traits. These traits also presented a low adjustment of the regression models used for the analyses, with R^2 values between 0.1 and 0.15, contrary to production and morphological traits, whose regression models presented R^2 values between 0.25 and 0.7 and yielded several significant THI effects during embryonic and fetal life, even when these effects were small.

In contrast to our results, several studies have shown substantial and significant effects of heat stress during the dam's gestation on the reproduction of the daughter. Akbarinejad et al. (2017) found significant detrimental effects of maternal heat stress for most of the primiparous fertility traits in Iranian cattle, with higher estimated effects when heat stress occurred during the last trimester of the gestation of the dam. The authors estimated a decrease of the first service conception rate for primiparous cows from 37.5% when there was no heat stress during the gestation, to 17.8% for gestations in which at least 2.5 mo of the last trimester occurred between June and August. Adverse effects of heat stress during the end of the gestation of the dam on progeny fertility were also reported by both Dahl et al. (2016) and Kipp et al. (2021). According to Dahl et al. (2016), heifers affected by late gestational heat stress required more services to conceive when compared with their herdmates under in utero thermoneutral conditions. Kipp et al. (2021) reported that heifers from dams exposed to high THI during the last 8 weeks of pregnancy presented a lower conception rate than those from dams exposed to high THI only during the 3 last weeks of gestation. Moreover, the authors reported that the interval from calving to first insemination for primiparous cows was prolonged when their dams were exposed to high THI during the last 2 mo of gestation. Other authors highlighted detrimental effects of heat stress at the beginning of the dam's gestation on the progeny's reproductive performances. For Holsteins from Florida, Pinedo and De Vries (2017) reported that cows conceived in winter exhibited the best reproductive performance (i.e., lower age at first calving and shorter calving-first breeding and calving-conception intervals). For Holsteins raised in Argentina, Recce et al. (2021) observed the most adverse effects of prenatal heat stress

when experienced by the dam during the first trimester of the gestation. The authors reported that cows exposed to a high THI (i.e., $\text{THI} \geq 72$) in the first trimester of their intrauterine development had longer intervals of calving to conception and calving to first service.

Our results have shown that for the French Holstein and Montbéliarde, the effects of in utero heat stress are weaker on subsequent performance than what is generally found in similar studies with other breeds or with equivalent breeds in different countries. In utero heat stress effects previously reported in the literature for the first lactation 305-d MY range from 200 to 900 kg (Barash et al., 1996 for Israeli cattle; Brown et al., 2015 and 2016, Laporta et al., 2020, and Pinedo and De Vries, 2017 for US cattle; and Van Eetvelde et al., 2017 for Belgian cattle). One could hypothesize that the small effect of maternal heat stress observed in our present study could be due to the moderate French climate (Vinet et al., 2023), as suggested in Kipp et al. (2021) in a similar study performed in Germany. However, in a study with 74 Holstein heifers reared in Belgium, a country with equivalently moderate climate (3% of the days in Belgium present THI above 68 according to Van Laer et al., 2014), Van Eetvelde et al. (2017) reported high effects of gestational heat stress on offspring performance, reporting a difference of 900 kg on 305-d energy-corrected milk yield. Finally, this difference was observed with a limited dataset and was not confirmed in a subsequent study by the same authors with a large dataset of Dutch and Belgian Holsteins (Van Eetvelde et al., 2020).

According to the results obtained with our data, high THI is unfavorable for progeny production traits (MY, FY, PY) when heat stress is experienced by the dam at the beginning of the gestation, during embryonic and early fetal life, but it is favorable when experienced by the dam at the end of the gestation. These negative effects of heat stress at the beginning of the gestation (and positive effects at the end of the gestation) on the progeny's production performance have also been reported by most studies analyzing the seasons of conception or the season of birth in warm regions. Barash et al. (1996) reported that Israeli Holstein cows born in summer and fall (i.e., cows potentially exposed to maternal heat stress at the end of the gestation) presented higher production than cows born in early spring (i.e., cows potentially exposed to maternal heat stress during the conception). Although it is more pronounced in first lactation, when the effect is around 240 kg greater milk yield for summer-fall born cows, this effect is observed for the first 3 parities (Barash et al., 1996).

In studies that compared US Holstein cows conceived in summer (June–August, i.e., potentially heat stress-conceived cows) with cows conceived in winter

(December–February, i.e., thermoneutral-conceived cows), Brown et al. (2015, 2016) had similar conclusions as Barash et al. (1996). In most instances of the studies from Brown et al. (2015, 2016), the thermoneutral-conceived cows produced significantly more milk than the heat stress conceived-cows. However, they observed a significant interaction between heat stress at the time of conception and season of calving, whereas a higher milk production of thermoneutral conceived cows was not observed for cows that calved in spring (Brown et al., 2015, 2016). Finally, the authors assumed that cows experiencing maternal heat stress around the time of conception may present better thermotolerance, giving them an advantage during subsequent periods of heat stress. Pinedo and De Vries (2017) have also observed that milk and fat production were generally greater for winter-conceived Holstein cows from Florida, compared with cows that were conceived in summer. As in Brown et al. (2015), this effect of the season of conception decreased with the parity of the cow (Pinedo and De Vries, 2017).

On a study that focused their analyses on the effect of heat stress at the end of the dam's gestation, Kipp et al. (2021) reported that daughters from dams who experienced the highest THI from wk 1 to 3 antepartum presented a lower first test-day MY than those not exposed to maternal antepartum heat stress; however, this negative effect was small (i.e., less than 0.1 kg/d) and not significant. Moreover, no negative effect was observed for the whole end of the gestation (8 wk antepartum), and events of THI ≥ 50 during weeks in greater distance from calving (i.e. wk 5 to 8) were associated with a minor increase of MY (Kipp et al., 2021). However, a THI of 50 can be considered too low to be associated with heat stress, and in many situations can in fact be considered an optimal climate condition for dairy cattle (Vinet et al., 2023).

Successive experiments were conducted in Florida comparing the effect of heat stress vs cooling during the last 46-d period of dams' gestations (Dado-Senn et al., 2020). These studies have shown that heifers that experienced late gestational heat stress produced less milk in their first lactation, compared with their counterparts that had their in utero development under thermoneutral conditions, i.e., dams that were actively cooled when the ambient temperature exceeded 21°C (Laporta et al., 2020). In these experiments, the decrease observed in milk production of in utero heat-stressed heifers was remarkable, with losses ranging from 2.2 kg to 5.1 kg per diem for wk 1 to 35 of the first lactation, depending on the datasets analyzed by each study (Dahl et al., 2016; Monteiro et al., 2016a; Laporta et al., 2020). Moreover, lower body weights from birth to one year of age have been reported for heifers from late-gestational

heat-stressed dams, but no association has been found between this lower weight in the heifer's first year and its later milk production through the first lactation (Monteiro et al., 2016a; Dado-Senn et al., 2020). Furthermore, mammary biopsies collected from first-lactation heifers showed that in utero heat-stressed heifers had smaller mammary alveoli comprising fewer mammary epithelial cells, as well as a lower rate of mammary epithelial cell proliferation, relative to heifers that did not experience heat stress in utero (Skibieli et al., 2018a; Dado-Senn et al., 2020). Finally, in these last studies, the negative effect of late in utero heat stress was observed across lactations for milk, fat, protein, and lactose yields.

Although Monteiro et al. (2016a) observed no heat stress effect at the end of maternal gestation (the sole period investigated in their study) on the progeny's SCS during their first lactation, Kipp et al. (2021) observed a trend similar to ours for this trait, with a decrease in SCS when THI is higher at the end of gestation (for SCS, a decrease is a favorable effect). In the latter study, the positive effect of higher THI at the end of the dam's gestation was small, but the estimated difference between the extreme THI classes (i.e., THI ≤ 39 vs THI ≥ 60) was significant ($P < 0.05$) between 29 and 56 d prepartum. Although studies are available on the effect of prenatal heat stress on the progeny's SCS, such studies on the adult progeny's pathologies are still rare in cattle. We studied mastitis indicators, but our data did not show any adverse effect of a high THI during in utero development on the subsequent occurrence of clinical mastitis, and to our knowledge, no other study has done so.

In their experiments that compared the effect of heat stress versus cooling during the last 46-d period of gestation of dams, beyond birth and one-year-old weight, Monteiro et al. (2016a) also studied BCS at calving, yet they did not observe significant differences between the 2 groups. These results are somewhat at odds with our own, considering that we have observed differences in primiparous BCS, probably due to differences in THI during in utero development. However, the differences we observed are extremely small, and we do not know whether they are consistent with differences that might exist on birth weight. For our study, we chose not to study birth weight due to a lack of reliable information about birth weight for the French dairy cattle records.

Several hypotheses have been proposed to explain the long-term effects of heat stress during the dam's pregnancy, but the biological processes involved in the long-term effects of in utero heat stress are not fully defined. These hypotheses mainly concern changes in hormonal profiles or epigenetic modifications during embryonic or fetal development, with lasting consequences throughout the animal's life. Despite conflicting results and

hypotheses concerning the effect of heat stress during maternal gestation on blood insulin concentration in neonatal calves, several authors suggested that this hormone could explain the differences in performance between stressed and unstressed calves during in utero life. Van Eetvelde et al. (2017) reported a negative correlation between the neonatal basal insulin concentrations and the environmental temperature at birth. Moreover, the same study reported that winter-born heifers presented the highest basal insulin concentrations 3 d after birth, whereas glucose concentrations were similar irrespective of the season of birth. According to the authors, this last result suggested a lower insulin sensitivity of peripheral tissues. They therefore concluded that, conversely, heifers born in the warmer months, with higher peripheral insulin sensitivity at birth, might later develop higher insulin resistance and better tissue accretion, including mammary tissue, ultimately leading to a higher first lactation milk yields. Conversely, Monteiro et al. (2016b) observed no differences in plasma insulin or in glucose concentration from d 1 to d 56 after birth between heat-stressed and cooled calves during the end of their dam's gestation. Nevertheless, after a glucose tolerance test and after an insulin challenge, the 2 groups diverged in their responses in glucose, insulin, and nonesterified fatty acid concentrations. Monteiro et al. (2016b) suggested that compared with cooled calves, heat-stressed calves exhibited a relatively high level of insulin resistance in peripheral tissues, such as muscle and adipose tissue, and thus limited insulin-mediated glucose entry into the peripheral tissues. However, the authors did not hypothesize that these alterations persist into maturity and whether they can account for any reduced milk production during first and second lactations (Ouellet et al., 2020).

Using different methodologies, such as analyzing the performance of offspring from ancestors that did or did not experience heat stress during pregnancy over several generations, or studying the methylome and transcriptome of these offspring, several authors have suggested that heat stress during the dam's pregnancy can modify the epigenetic marks of the fetus. Weller et al. (2021) found a significant association of the month of birth, the season of pregnancy, and the heat stress index of F_0 females, with the performance of their F_2 and F_3 progenies. To explain the inheritance of the environmental effect experienced by the F_0 ancestors, these authors hypothesized that an epigenetic modification that occurred during the formation of the F_1 gametes could be preserved, at least partially, during the formation of the F_2 gametes. In other words, they suspected an inefficient restoration or erasure of the epigenetic marks (Weller et al., 2021). Similar transgenerational effects due to heat stress during the F_0

gestation on their F_2 or F_3 progeny were confirmed by both Laporta et al. (2020) and Macciotta et al. (2023).

Such modifications of epigenetic marks due to heat stress were highlighted by Skibieli et al. (2018b) who identified a substantial number of differentially expressed genes and differentially methylated cytosines from a comparison of gene expression profiles and methylation patterns of in utero heat-stressed or cooled calves. The differences in pattern of methylation between heat-stressed or cooled calves were observed on 2 different tissues: liver tissue of the male calves collected just after the birth, and mammary gland tissue of the 2-yr lactating females. Interestingly, among the differently methylated genes (i.e., genes with at least one differently methylated cytosine) that were identified between the heat-stressed and the cooled groups, Skibieli et al. (2018b) reported 50 genes or ribosomal RNA that were common to both tissues examined. This result led the authors to suggest that there are common patterns of DNA methylation that were induced by heat stress, regardless of the animal's sex, age, or tissue type. Finally, these methylation patterns may affect fundamental processes, including cellular repair, oxidative defense, energy metabolism, and development (Skibieli et al., 2018b). Lastly, although the general biological functions of the differentially methylated genes were similar to the biological functions of the differentially expressed genes, the authors found weak correlations between changes in methylation patterns and changes in gene expression. Our results did not address epigenetic effects, but such phenomena could explain the persistence of differences between those animals that were exposed to in utero stress, and those that were not, throughout their lives.

Most studies available in the literature of in utero heat stress have investigated the effects of heat stress either at the early stages of the dam's gestation (warm or thermoneutral months of conception, sometimes excluding other months of birth, as in Brown et al., 2015, 2016), or at the late stages of the dam's gestation (month of calf birth, effect of THI on late-gestation stages). As a result, the beginning and the end of the gestation are the periods most often reported to be sensitive to heat stress. Nevertheless, of the few studies that considered all gestation stages, Akbarinejad et al. (2017) and Recce et al. (2021) reported that the second trimester of the dam's gestation was also potentially sensitive to heat stress. In our study, the progeny's production traits and SCS were shown to be negatively affected by high THI during the dam's early gestation, whereas morphological traits would be more affected by high THI during the dam's mid-gestation.

We would like to make a remark that, although the THI for different gestational periods were tested in-

dependently, this independence is not true. Due to the bovine gestation length and the temperate climate in mainland France, cows that experience heat stress (THI >65) during the last trimester of their pregnancy are likely to consistently experience an average THI below 65 during the first trimester of their pregnancy (Supplemental Figure S2, see Notes). In other words, cows that experienced a high THI at the end of the gestation are cows whose pregnancies began during the colder seasons. Therefore, we cannot eliminate the hypothesis that the positive effects of high THI during the last months of gestation may be a consequence of the positive effects of an absence of high THI at the beginning of the dam's pregnancy. We did test some models that included not one, but 2 average monthly THI, one for the beginning and the other for the end of the dam's pregnancy. These monthly THI were considered either as 2 separated effects, or as their combination. Due to the partial dependence of the THI at the beginning and end of the gestation period, some combinations were not observed. However, these models did not suggest different results (not shown) from those reported as the main results from our study: a negative effect of high THI on production only when experienced by the dams at the beginning of their pregnancy, and a positive effect of high THI on production when experienced by the dams in the last part of their pregnancy.

When compiling the results from all previous studies regarding the effects of prenatal heat stress, along with ours, it is in fact difficult to define one single period of a dam's pregnancy that is more sensitive to heat stress than others, with respect to their effects on the later performances of the gestated progeny. It is likely that in utero heat stress has multiple effects on embryos and fetuses. These effects include a decrease in nutrient intake due to reduced maternal intake, fetal hypoxia and malnutrition due to reduced blood flow to the uterus, the modification of epigenetic reprogramming (Ghaffari, 2022), and changes in the balance between reactive oxygen generation and antioxidant protection (Hansen, 2013). Finally, it is possible that the sensitivity to each of these phenomena differs according to the stage of development of the embryo or fetus, and that long-term effects on the progeny are due to multiple processes.

CONCLUSIONS

Our study estimated the effect of heat stress during the dam's pregnancy on different performance metrics of the future progeny during their first lactation for the French Holstein and Montbéliarde breeds. This effect was estimated as the deviation of the observed performance from the expected one. In both breeds and for all traits, THI

effects during gestation appeared to have little impact on adult performance under French climatic conditions. Although results on fertility and udder health were not significant, milk, fat, and protein yields were more sensitive to heat stress at the beginning than at the end of the gestation. This study was carried out with data from animals exposed to a rather temperate climate, and we cannot exclude that the impact of stress may be stronger for animals exposed to warmer weather.

NOTES

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Nonstandard abbreviations used: CRc = conception rate at first insemination for cows; CRh = conception rate at first insemination for heifers; Depth = body depth; FY = 305-d fat yield; Height = height at sacrum; HOL = Holstein; M1–M9 = gestational months 1 to 9, in 30-d increments; M9.5 = last period of gestation, from d 250 to 279; Mast = clinical mastitis occurrence; MastNb = number of clinical mastitis events; MON = Montbéliarde; MuscT = muscularity at thighs; MuscW = muscularity at withers; MY = 305-d milk yield; PY = 305-d protein yield; SAFRAN = Système d'Analyse Fournissant des Renseignements Atmosphériques à la Neige; THI = temperature-humidity index; Width = chest width.

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